

KEY CHALLENGES AND CONSIDERATIONS FOR DEVELOPING GLOBAL INDICATORS FOR CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION

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Under the Paris Agreement, the [Global Goal on Adaptation](#) (GGA) was established **to enhance adaptive capacity, strengthen resilience, and reduce vulnerability to climate change**, with a view to contributing to sustainable development and ensuring an adequate adaptation response in the context of the temperature goal. It aims to make adaptation progress measurable at the global level and provide inputs for the [Global Stocktake](#) (GST), a periodical assessment of the world's collective progress towards achieving the Paris Agreement's purpose and long-term goals.

DEVELOPING INDICATORS FOR ADAPTATION PRESENTS COMPLEX CHALLENGES

However, **measuring climate adaptation progress presents several complex technical and political challenges**. In the multilateral climate negotiation process, two successive work programmes were launched to operationalize the GGA: first, the Glasgow-Sharm el Sheikh work programme from 2022-2023, then the currently ongoing UAE-Belém work programme from 2024-2025.

*For a full **overview of the state of negotiations on the GGA** and the operationalization of the UAE Framework for Global Climate Resilience, SLYCAN Trust has just published a technical briefing that captures the state of play ahead of SB62. [Access it here as a concise reference document](#) for the political as well as technical process on the GGA in 2025 and beyond.*

The Glasgow-Sharm el Sheikh work programme resulted in a **framework with seven thematic and four dimensional global targets**, which are to be achieved by 2030 and progressively beyond. Now, the process focuses on identifying, refining, and developing indicators for measuring progress towards these targets, with the aim to agree on **"a manageable set of no more than 100 indicators"** at COP30 in November 2025.

Ahead of the UNFCCC June Climate Meetings in Bonn (SB62), **the following briefing explores key considerations and challenges for developing GGA indicators** that could contribute to effective and scaled-up climate adaptation action.

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Understanding indicators

To understand the power of global governance indicators and how to use them judiciously, it is necessary to **understand what indicators are and how they are produced.**

Governance indicators can be defined as “a named collection of rank-ordered data that purports to represent the past or projected performance of different units. The data are generated through a process that simplifies raw data about a complex social phenomenon.” (Davis et al., 2012: 73-4)

Indicators are usually developed with the purpose of comparing and evaluating units over time and/or space. Hence, this simplification process—the development of indicators—needs to result in a quantified scale, and is sometimes then translated into a rating, ranking, or grade of state performance.

While global performance indicators can in principle be developed for any kind of “unit,” global governance relies heavily upon **country performance indicators (CPI)**. CPIs differ in their complexity and the potential for contestation. **One intuitive way of differentiating between CPIs is between counts, ratios, and composites** (Merry, 2016).

Counts are the simplest kind of indicator.

For instance, counting the number of births per year in a state may be a technical challenge, but few experts would disagree on the definition or how to count it. However, simple counts are seldom used in isolation in CPIs, as they can easily be misleading without reference to total population. For example, births need to be turned into a ratio to render them comparable, such as the total number of live human births per 1,000 population for a given period, divided by the length of the period in years.

However, by far the most influential and controversial types of CPIs are composite indicators, which combine two or more counts or ratios that are determined to comprise the overarching phenomenon to be measured. For instance, the Human Development Index comprises GDP per capita, mean years of schooling, and life expectancy at birth. Such indicators can transform an ambiguous complex world into simple, accessible knowledge, offering an ostensibly scientific means of evaluating state performance, enabling citizens to hold their governments to account, and promising evidence for evidence-based policymaking.

CPIs can exert influence through a variety of mechanisms. First, they can catalyse a domestic policy response by providing new and credible information regarding the scale of a problem, enabling domestic actors to overcome opposition to policy change. Second, CPIs may be used by third parties to allocate resources and thereby generate economic incentives to improve the score on the CPI. Third, scoring low on an CPI may trigger status concerns among the government and potentially the general public, while scoring high may promise international recognition that can boost a government’s legitimacy and national esteem.

Research has shown that **CPIs can exert an independent and significant influence over states.** That means that absent the indicator, the policies of states would have been different, and that these policy changes were substantial (Kelley, 2019). This alludes to potential challenges and constraints of indicators, even if they are—as per the GGA decision—explicitly not meant as basis for comparison between countries. First of all, critics highlight how despite the appearance of objectivity, the process of developing indicators requires interpretation and is thus an inherently political process.

All CPIs—especially composite indicators—must simplify complexity and strip away context, running the risk of generating a policy “tunnel vision” that necessarily excludes context that might be considered vital for good policymaking. The challenges in simplifying and selecting, together with the difficulty of challenging CPIs once they are developed, have led to CPIs being criticized for undermining democratic processes (Beaumont and Towns, 2021).

Crucially for climate adaption indicators, this can undermine a CPI’s legitimacy and effectiveness if they become seen as a one size fits all measure imposed by experts based in the global north. This challenge speaks to the **necessity of fostering inclusive processes both to ensure the relevance of the indicator to the countries they measure and their legitimacy** once developed.

Moreover, **the choice of what to measure is often heavily influenced by the costs**. Rather than selecting the optimum measures that align with the definition of the concept, CPIs must make do with the data they can afford to gather. For these reasons, most CPIs rely upon imperfect proxies or stand-in measures that reflect the underlying phenomenon to varying degrees. **The necessity of simplifying and using cost-effective proxies can also generate opportunities for “gaming” the CPI**. When economic or social incentives are attached to a CPI, it generates incentives to “cheat” the indicator by focusing on improving the measure rather than the real performance in the underlying quality that is assessed. This general feature of governance indicators is highly salient to the question of whether and how climate finance should be tied to adaption indicators.

Developing indicators for adaptation

Developing good indicators for climate change adaptation presents several specific challenges:

- First, adaptation encompasses a multitude of possible actions that are highly context-specific and can range from biophysical to economic, socio-cultural, or environmental practices, methods, or assets.
- Second, adaptation can work to moderate harm (i.e., preserve the status quo) as well as to take advantage of beneficial opportunities, implying different criteria and metrics for success.
- Third, adaptation can be applied to both human and natural systems and often operates at the intersection of the two—for example, in sectors such as food, or health.

Refinement and development of indicators for the GGA takes place under the UAE-Belém work programme launched at COP28 in late 2023.

This programme aims to **identify and, as needed, develop indicators and potential quantified elements for measuring progress towards eleven global targets**, covering key adaptation sectors as well as the adaptation policy cycle (consisting of impact, vulnerability, and risk assessment; planning; implementation; and monitoring, evaluation, and learning).

As emphasized in [decision 2/CMA.5](#), “adaptation action should be continuous, iterative and progressive” as well as “based on and guided by the best available science,” which includes, as appropriate, the use of science-based indicators, metrics and targets, traditional knowledge, Indigenous Peoples’ knowledge, local knowledge systems, ecosystem-based adaptation, nature-based solutions, locally led and community-based adaptation, disaster risk reduction, intersectional approaches, private sector engagement, maladaptation avoidance, the recognition of adaptation co-benefits, and sustainable development.

To assist in the work of reviewing, refining, mapping, and developing indicators, technical experts were convened to cover all eleven targets. After almost a year of work, these experts have now prepared [a consolidated list of 490 indicator options](#) by unpacking the targets into sub-components, mapping indicators to these sub-components, and reviewing them against a list of criteria.

This preliminary list of indicators comprises both count- and ratio-based options. In addition, many expert groups have included headline indicators with associated sub-indicators that allow for disaggregation or act as composite indicators.

For example, one headline indicator under target 9c (health) focuses on the incidence of climate-sensitive infectious diseases, acting as an umbrella for sub-indicators on specific diseases (e.g., dengue, malaria, or Lyme disease). Another example is the headline indicator for “number of countries with operational, multi-hazard, climate- and community-informed early warning systems,” under target 9e (infrastructure and human settlements), which combines the existence of multi-hazard early warning systems, integration of climate forecasts, community participation, and percentage of urban population covered into a composite indicator.

Such composite measures, especially when they attempt to measure heavily contested concepts, often generate considerable debate around which measures they select and what is excluded: for instance, the HDI has come under fire for relying on GDP per capita and overlooking various kinds of inequality in distribution. **A composite measure of climate adaptation would inevitably face similar tough choices between coverage and capturing complexity, parsimony, and legibility.**

While not all indicators in the consolidated list explicitly define their unit, the GGA intends to capture global adaptation progress through a country-driven process.

It could therefore be assumed that a significant proportion of indicators will be CPIs reported at the national level, although this reporting will be voluntary and is not meant to create additional reporting burdens on countries, particularly on developing countries. In addition, **indicators for means of implementation (including finance, technology, and capacity-building)** for adaptation have been a key part of the discussion, and relevant indicator options have been included in the consolidated list across all targets.

For adaptation in particular, the question of indicators is therefore closely linked to support provided and received, potentially with ripple effects affecting actors outside the UNFCCC process, such as philanthropies, international financial institutions, or private sector. Further, if these indicators are not carefully designed, they could cause an incomplete or misleading assessment of global adaptation progress, compromising the purpose of the GGA and GST.

A dilemma is also presented by the attempt to include indicators that count all important context for adaption. This either risks indicators becoming so complex that they lose their legibility to policymakers; creating a set of indicators that are comprehensive in scope, but not relevant for many of the countries they measure; or using a simplified measure that is legible to policymakers but potentially missing essential context for decision-making.

References

- *Beaumont, P., & Towns, A. E. (2021). The rankings game: A relational approach to country performance indicators. International Studies Review, 23(4), 1467-1494.*
- *Davis, K. E., Kingsbury, B., & Merry, S. E. (2012). Indicators as a technology of global governance. Law & Society Review, 46(1), 71-104. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5893.2012.00473.x>*
- *Kelley, J. G., & Simmons, B. A. (2019). Introduction: The power of global performance indicators. International Organization, 73(3), 491-510.*
- *Merry, S. E. (2016). The seductions of quantification: Measuring human rights, gender violence, and sex trafficking. University of Chicago Press.*

Towards an effective Global Goal on Adaptation

When negotiators and experts continue their work towards a final list of indicators, there are some key recommendations to avoid or at least mitigate these challenges and constraints. The first and most would be to accept and recognise that no indicator is perfect: due to the simplification processes involved in their construction, they will present a partial view that is potentially useful but never paints the whole picture. Country representatives and experts can seek answers to several fundamental questions that will help them avoid potential issues associated with indicator development and use:

- What potentially salient information on to the issue does the indicator not measure?
- What are the political and economic interests at stake in measuring the phenomenon in the way that the indicator does?
- What other indicators are available on the issue and how do they compare?
- Is there any public criticism of the measure and what do these critics highlight?
- Is there evidence of cheating among other countries that render the final verdict of the CPI questionable?
- To what extent do the indicators' measures reflect national and global priorities that were determined through inclusive and participatory processes?
- How do the indicators account for the voluntary nature of reporting towards the GGA and the need to avoid additional burdens on developing countries?
- Given the answers to these questions, is it politically and analytically defensible to use the indicator to inform public adaptation policymaking?

Outcomes on the GGA indicators at COP30 present a unique opportunity for climate adaptation and other related matters to build on work conducted by both negotiators and experts as well as multiple stakeholders and presents the potential to identify measurable approaches for adaptation action.

It is important to ensure that the finalized indicators are applicable across different contexts, are not detrimental to developing countries where climate action is most needed and are applied for ensuring the goals of the Paris Agreement are met, and means of implementation are scaled up and accessed for adaptation action. **Therefore, the selection of the final indicators needs to take into consideration general approaches to indicator development, especially their applicability in country-specific contexts and their relevance to adaptation.**

Organizational profile

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